

OPPORTUNITIES TO WIDELY USE UZBEK FOLK ART CIRCLE COURSES IN DIRECTING YOUNG PEOPLE TO THE PROFESSION

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Abstract: This article talks about the role of national crafts and folk art clubs in educating students in the spirit of national values and traditions.

Key words: education, training, profession, craft, labor, treasure, need, folk craft, circle, painting, jewelry, customs, traditions, embroidery, pottery.

As soon as independence was declared in Uzbekistan, great attention was paid to creating decent living and working conditions for people, increasing people's well-being, establishing the principles of social justice, and educating the growing young generation in the spirit of humanity. In today's conditions, labor and professional training of young people is an important social task, and theorists and practitioners of this field, pedagogic scientists, teachers, trainers, trainers and masters teach young people various aspects of folk crafts, prepare them to acquire professions in these directions. will lead to development, promotion and thereby becoming a worthy contribution to the treasury of world culture. National customs, traditions, the living conditions of the peoples include the national features, passed through the complex tests called life for thousands of years, and rose to the level of the unique constitution and law of the people. With the honor of independence, conditions have been created to study and put into practice the priceless heritage left by our ancestors. In the present period, the improvement of education and training work, nationalization, to the level corresponding to world standards

special importance should be given to our rich national and cultural heritage, national and universal values, and new requirements of the new era. First of all, this requires the training of highly qualified teachers who can widely use modern educational forms, tools and methods. It should be noted that education cannot be separated from each other. The fact that the organization of educational activities is directed to a certain profession, naturally, the feeling of love for work does not automatically develop in students. It is formed by the personal example of parents or other adults in the family, and by studying the traditions of hard work accumulated by the human society in the trainings related to technology education held in educational institutions. In a word, the main goal of technology education is to focus the students' knowledge and experience gained from life on the creation of content for the secrets of the primary profession by finding solutions to problems with specific production content. In order to conduct interesting, effective and fulfilling technology education classes organized in general education schools, the teacher should have intellectual, spiritual, methodological, general work, special professional, calculation, measurement-checking, drawing and composition skills. should have such qualities as the ability to manage various devices, technological processes, direct labor objects, objects and weapons.

In his address to the Oliy Majlis on December 28, 2018, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, specifically emphasized that "... it is necessary to reduce unemployment among the population, increase the income of people and families." Of course, it is not a secret to anyone that the fulfillment of such a noble task is carried out by creating and increasing jobs. Therefore, creating a job is one of the most complex and serious tasks. One of the ways to solve this in the local conditions is national for students teaching crafts. Because in most cases, national handicrafts are considered to be one of the industries that do not require complex equipment and tools, and raw materials can be found and prepared locally. Of course, these things can be done at school and in non-school children's institutions.

Folk crafts are painting, jewelry, jewelry, wood carving, metal carving, embroidery, tanning, cooking, wood burning, pottery, blacksmithing, carpentry, carpentry, blacksmithing, cutlery, tool making, such as locksmithing, coppersmithing, needlework

It has more than 150 fields and has many features of labor and vocational education - practicality, creativity, nationalism, ease of finding and using local raw materials, the uniqueness of the labor of boys and girls. , is distinguished by its ability to combine urban and rural schools, does not require complex devices, equipment, tools and machines in the main cases, and the simplicity of organizing classes. As a result, the fact that young people who have sufficiently studied this field, who have acquired certain professions do not remain unemployed, and the competitiveness of the labor market, is of particular note. The art of folk crafts is based on the skills and abilities of enriching national values and traditions by consistently studying, developing and improving them. Therefore, the Law "On Education" states: "General secondary education is the main link in the continuous state education system, and students receive scientific knowledge, labor and primary it ensures the development of professional skills, business fundamentals, as well as creative abilities and spiritual qualities", it was noted. Folk crafts help to form young people's thinking, imagination, aesthetic taste, dexterity. After all, these qualities and qualities have an effective impact on the comprehensive development of the young generation. Indeed, as long as there are people, this art will live.

No matter what kind of craft there is in the world, there will certainly be its masters and its students. There are masters of painting, goldsmithing, coppersmithing, knife making, felt making, carpet making, goldsmithing, wood carving, basket maker, blacksmith, bone carver, stone smith, carpenter, jeweler and other craftsmen. At a time when great attention is being paid to the development of national crafts, teachers teach their students their crafts based on our Uzbek national traditions are coming. Every craft has been considered sacred since ancient times, and they were respected and revered. Our forefathers developed specific standards of etiquette, special procedures, customs, behavior culture, and national traditions for teachers and students, and strictly followed them.

Uzbek folk decorative art circles are especially noteworthy among the circles of fine arts. The variety of Uzbek folk decorative art attracts people and arouses interest in it. The circle of Uzbek folk applied decorative art is a continuation of the knowledge received in fine art classes. Circles of folk applied decorative art are associations gathered by the will of those interested in this art. The secrets of this art are taught on the basis of a special scientific and practical program in the folk decorative art classes.

The purpose of Uzbek folk decorative art circles:

- to learn to perceive, enjoy and evaluate the surrounding events and beauties;
- educating the participants in an aesthetic spirit, making them ideologically, morally polite, hardworking;
- increase the research and creativity skills of the participants;
- increasing interest in art;
- instilling love for Uzbek folk decorative art;
- folk decorative art and its types, formation of execution technology and skills, education of love for work and help in choosing a profession in the future, etc.

The age, ability and level of knowledge of the participants of the circle are taken into account in the implementation of the goal. The leader of the group examines the age, ability and level of knowledge of the participants and divides them into small groups, medium groups and large groups. Newly admitted participants in the small group attend one year, then move to the middle group, and they also move to the large group after a year.

Two (large and small) rooms should be allocated for conducting folk decorative arts training. Theoretical training is held in a large room. The room should be spacious, bright and clean. It is recommended to have the following equipment in the room where folk decorative art classes are held:

- sink, table and chairs, blackboard;
- corner of the club (it should include the history of the club, the lesson schedule, duties of the staff, activists of the club, etc.);
- organization of stands related to folk decorative art and its types;
- racks and cabinets, epidiascope, diascope and other technical devices;
- lamps that illuminate the room;
- there should be two types of curtains on the windows, one of which is a simple curtain, and the other is a curtain that can be closed when showing slides or movies;
- albums, books, dictionaries related to folk decorative art, stands dedicated to the work of masters, medical corner, wall newspapers, weekly news, a blackboard for newspaper articles (the last week's news is posted), etc.

Specialists who have graduated from special secondary and higher educational institutions, and masters of folk decorative art can conduct folk decorative arts club classes. The head of the circle should also consider that there will be 12-15 participants in one group when dividing the participants into groups. Also, before attracting participants to the club, the leader should create all the necessary conditions, then the leader should write an announcement about the organization of the club and hang it in places, go to nearby organizations, talk to representatives of local trade union organizations, the head of the school, and together should carry out explanatory work. It gives a good result. A large number of participants are enrolled in the first organized club, but the head of the club writes a separate letter and gives information about the participants' name, surname, work, education, residence, if they are a school student, about their parents. must write down the information. It is known that schoolchildren (11-12 years old) are curious about everything, and they can be members of another club. Therefore, the leader should pay serious attention to the selection of students for the club.

A basic and general understanding is given to the participant who is drawing a composition so that he can work independently. From the correct handling of the tools to the finishing of the work, importance is explained. Every hour

It is necessary to give a break of 5-10 minutes, because fatigue leads to slow, unintelligent actions, which affects the psychology of the participants. Therefore, during the training, it is appropriate to talk about the folk decorative art or tell about the life of its masters. The leader should follow the following principles when working with the circle participants:

- the direction of the training should be aimed at educating the participants in the spirit of creativity;
- taking into account the ability level and personal interests of the participants;
- the work of the club should be useful to the public and the community;
- the life of the club should be aimed at the independence, creative activity and initiative of the participants.

In the correct organization of group activities, it is necessary to connect with botany, geometry, geography, history, natural science, mathematics, mother tongue, physics and other subjects through demonstration samples. In order to lead the club well, the leader should know modern didactics well, be able to apply it creatively in practice, and the following are the didactics in pedagogical activities:

- the unity of education and upbringing, being scientific, demonstrative, conscious, active and independent, systematic and consistent of education, suitable for participants, thorough and consistent development of knowledge, skills and abilities it is necessary that the mastery of the theory is related to the practice, and the principles of teaching should be taken into account for the characteristics of each student.

We recommend that Uzbek folk art circles have the following visual aids:

for a small group: posters, slides and slides on topics;

for the middle group: posters about the master's pattern compositions, circular pattern compositions used in pottery, wood carving, hankhkor, posters about manifestation and its types, photo posters about the practical art of brotherly peoples, woodwork of brotherly peoples, pattern elements used in bone, stone, etc., samples of participants' composition works;

for a large group: pattern compositions adapted to wood carving, rough copies drawn adapted to carpets, group elements and composition posters, posters made of photos of bone, wood and ganch carving grids, posters made of carved khontakhts.

Technical tools play a leading role in the positive organization of Uzbek folk decorative arts club training. Although special workshops and offices are allocated in many circles, they are not provided with special equipment, including film cameras, epidiascopes, televisions, and diascope. The use of technical tools enriches the knowledge of the participants and increases their interest in art. Conversations about art are of great importance in imparting knowledge to the participants of the circle. In order not to bore the participants, it is recommended to use the exhibition properly and conduct a conversation.

As we know, Uzbek folk art, like all arts, has its own terms. One of the reasons why the current folk art circles are not in a satisfactory condition is that the terms of folk decorative art, created as a result of the creative work of our people over the centuries, are not well studied. It turned out that the participants do not know the dictionary meaning of the terms. For this reason, the leader of the circle should study and master the terms of folk art in order to make the training meaningful and interesting; to provide students with a dictionary of special terms from Uzbek folk art in order to understand the dictionary meaning;

the leader of the circle should organize a special card file, that is, he should collect and study terms from folk art;

during the training, he writes and explains the dictionary meaning of the terms to the members of the circle, even if they are small;

It is advisable to create a stand called an explanatory dictionary of Uzbek folk art and hang it in the room.

We recommend writing approximately the following terms on such a stand.

Bofta is an element of a plant-like pattern. An attractive shape formed by the winding of the trunk. Bofta is used in all types of folk art. It has straight, curved and mixed line types.

Ganchhok is a mixture made by mixing soil, sand and ganch with water. One part of sand, one part of sand, and one part of fine soil are mixed in the preparation of ganchkhok. Mix the water well until it becomes a thick paste and then spray it on the wall.

Namoyan means view, landscape in Persian. Russian panel. The most perfect mature pattern composition ever. It reflects a generalized pictorial image of visible reality. For example, it shows fields, gardens, rivers, flowers, leaves, etc. The edge of the image often plays an important role in the artistic rendering of the image. An image is an independent composition that does not connect anywhere.

Targhil is the decoration of the flowers and leaves of the pattern with the help of different colored lines. In painting, it is a type of decorative painting, and painters depict flowers and leaves in nature, their shadows, with the help of colored lines. He also draws and paints the seeds and pollen of flowers in nature to finish the pattern.

A master is a person who has mastered a trade and gained competence in this field. A person who knows his craft well.

Extracurricular activities play an important role in solving the educational issues faced by the folk art circle, because they serve as an important factor in strengthening the knowledge and experience of the participants, and in forming their worldview. .

In addition to training, it is advisable to organize the following activities:

- excursion to museums of fine art, folk decorative art, history, places of work of ganch, wood, and stone carvers, architectural monuments, and a bird's circle;
- holding meetings with folk decorative art masters, art historians and others in Uzbekistan;
- organization of exhibitions of participants' works;
- Regular publication of wall newspapers named "Yosh Ustalar";
- Organization of panels on the topics of "Skillful hands", "Our masters", "Beauty owners", "Famous carving masters";
- making photo albums of works of famous masters and works of participants;
- preparation of creative magazines dedicated to the life and work of young carpenters;
- conducting contests among participants; organization of quizzes;
- showing slides and films about folk decorative art, architectural monuments, etc. during non-training hours.

Based on the program established by the circle of folk applied decorative arts, circle participants must implement the following requirements in life:

1. The role of Uzbek folk decorative art in life and its importance;
2. Ability to work with all materials used in folk decorative art;
3. Ability to work freely on various tools;
4. Ability to draw types of patterns and their elements;
5. Be able to create plant-like, geometric, symbolic and other types of patterns;
6. To be able to use these patterns in folk arts;

7. To be able to make items of folk decorative art;
8. Keeping the workplace clean, knowing the rules of equipment safety, fire safety and hygiene;
9. Effective use of working time;
10. To be able to know the organization of the workplace and the most advanced methods of work;
11. Knowing that they should be able to read and analyze the works of uncomplicated folk decorative art.

Each participant who has fully mastered the training program of this club can work as a teacher of folk arts and a leader of a club at the house of culture in different places.

The Uzbek people are famous all over the world for their ancient and rich culture. Ancient monuments and underground part of Uzbekistan is a huge historical museum. Every architectural monument in Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Tashkent, Termiz and other cities is a great work, rare manuscripts, and examples of folk art. built buildings, architectural decorations, their diversity, geometric and plant-like patterns, their composite image invites people to enjoy, educate, express their dreams, hopes, and love through them. Our cultural wealth acquired over the centuries, some types of folk art, their specific aspects, the technology of working with real Uzbek names, and the names of our masters who created them are gradually being forgotten. Therefore, preserving, appreciating and using the historical monuments and other practical arts created as a result of the creative work of our people over the centuries is one of the most important tasks of our time.

The aim is to use it for the development of the national tradition of cultural heritage and high art, to introduce creative practice methods in it, to work with natural materials, to instill in people, especially young people, perseverance, perseverance, and interesting unique types of folk art. is appropriate.

Color painting is the art of harmony of color and light.

When depicting reality with the help of paints, it is necessary to take into account the effect of colors on each other and depict them based on the harmony of colors. It is important to note that the right combination of colors in the image creates the basis for the development of knowledge of the beauty of an elegant work, along with the ability to understand beauty.

Color is important in applied arts such as painting, pottery, embroidery, carpet making, jewelry, goldsmithing, painting, etc. Color is especially important in the art of painting. In the school of painting, each master has his own colors. The common color in Khorezm schools of painting and architectural patterns is blue, which coolness, listening i.e. symmetrical colors are used. Especially, looking at the architectural patterns, the patterns decorated in airy colors give a unique charm. In the Khiva school of painting, the main color is cold, i.e. blue.

The Tashkent school of painting is based on green, brown and air colors. Jalil Khakimov worked mainly in green color. The colors of the pattern compositions are elegant, close to each other and done with great accuracy.

Makhmud Turayev, the current representative of the Tashkent school of painting, works in pink, purple, green, and brown colors. The patterns made in each color have their own charm and appearance. It is made in both dark and light colors. Tayir Tukhtakhojayev skillfully decorated buildings and objects in his unique brown hexagon color. If you take a look at the patterned compositions, the warm colors will give a person an upbeat spirit and a festive mood. Saidakhmad Makhmudov, a representative of the Fargona school of painting, generally

obeys colors in his pattern compositions, but in many patterns, the ground is made by playing with the contrast of warm colors and cold colors.

In this manifestation, the contrast between warm and cold colors is given, and each color of the background has its own charm. These patterns are made in the natural colors of the Fergana Valley. Leaves and flowers are painted in warm and cold colors.

Anvar Ilkhomov continues the work of his teacher Jalil Khakimov, making patterns in green and other colors based on tradition.

In practical arts such as painting, pottery, embroidery, etc., the color is one color, for example, blue, green, red, brown, purple. is based on the dominance of pink, other colors are subordinated to it.

A set of unique aspects of an object or building is also called a color. The specific features of the work of art, i.e. era, nationality, psychological state, general reality, etc., are highlighted.

Today, we have a culture of educating young people. from our values, examples of our national art, great importance is attached to the wide use of wonderful art examples created by our ancestors and known throughout the world.

Colorful plant-like, geometric patterns, their mutual location is deeply meaningful. Symbolism is paramount in the depicted motifs. Our ancestors decorated ancient monuments with elegant patterns and sang their hopes, love and wishes through them. Our painter ancestors studied the human psyche very deeply and from all sides and enriched the houses with wonderful patterns. Based on life experiences, wise grandfathers learned that in a designed house, people can be calm, have peace of mind, and live a long life. In order to learn the language of the art of painting, foreign painters have completely mastered the rules of composition, the symbolic alphabet of each element and color of the pattern.

Currently, the issue of using the traditions of "Teacher-disciple etiquette" in the educational system, especially in professional circles, remains one of the important problems that have not been sufficiently studied. Because the current education system demands not only professional skills and qualifications, but also personal qualities. In the process of the education system in Uzbekistan, all conditions are being created for the formation of a creative, active, spiritually rich person. But today, although favorable conditions have been created for the training of qualified specialists, we cannot fully use the rich heritage and experience of our ancestors.

Many years of research have shown that there are many problems specific to folk architects and folk craftsmen, including the history of the national patterns of the Uzbek people, the experiences of their schools, masters, master-apprentice traditions, the symbolic alphabet of decorations, artistic analysis of works. and others to learn to their deep roots. Therefore, we do not have the right to forget our huge cultural wealth over the centuries, in particular, the unique aspects of the widespread types of the Uzbek national folk decorative border, schools, methods of execution technology, and the blessed names of the masters who created them.

That is why it is our important task to preserve these unique border masterpieces, to study them scientifically, to teach them to young people and to pass them on to the next generation.

There are total patterns created by Uzbek folk masters, which are also subject to specific laws and rules that acquire a conditional image of nature and reality. These laws are derived from nature itself. No matter what plant you take, it grows only in one direction. For example, a willow tree looks like it is growing upside down, but in reality it grows from the root to the body, from the trunk to the branch, from the branch to the leaf, continuing in one direction.

This law of nature is reflected in the pattern. When drawing a pattern composition, every master should try not to fill the surface of the paper with patterns, but to consciously follow the laws of nature and art to fully illuminate the landscape and image. That is why the most difficult and responsible stage in the artist's work is drawing the composition of the pattern.

In conclusion, the goal of us teachers of applied arts is to make students become highly qualified specialists and have high taste, mother, by widening the effective use of local resources for the all-round development of the individual in the conditions of independent Uzbekistan. loyalty to the motherland, to ensure that they grow up to be people who know the art of national and world peoples perfectly, who can love and appreciate our past culture created by our ancestors.

In addition to developing aesthetic taste in students, the imparted knowledge of folk art serves to form a culture of perception of existence and a positive attitude in them. They also help students to understand the aesthetic essence of works of decorative applied art.

Today, it is very important to direct young people to the profession, to increase their interest in various professions, to respect their professions and to form feelings of pride. Because the future fate of our great country is closely related to this issue.

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